

Problems Encountered During the use of Pedagogical Technologies in Physical Education Lessons

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Abstract:

This article describes in detail the effective aspects of using innovative pedagogical technologies in physical education classes, their importance, as well as several innovative pedagogical technologies that serve to ensure quality.

Keywords: pedagogical technology, education, interactive method, modern technology, skills.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era, it is a requirement of the time for teachers to have high professional training, pedagogical skills, high spiritual and moral qualities, and deep knowledge of ideology, and effective use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods in educational work.

As the most important part of the great creative work that is being carried out in order to ensure that the young generation grows up to be mature, educated, highly moral, well-rounded and patriotic individuals, measures are taken to ensure that pedagogues-employees acquire high scientific and methodical knowledge and high skills in practical work. is an increase.

Serious attention has been paid to this issue since the first years of our country's independence. The President clearly expressed the following thoughts:

"School, education issues are under the control of the state and society. It is stipulated in our Basic Law. At the same time, it is a general issue that requires the participation and support of the general public."

Currently, improving the effectiveness of education in every school is a serious task. For this, every teacher is required to be familiar with the most effective modern pedagogical technologies of

teaching his subject and to regularly improve his professional skills by continuously studying the innovations in this field.

It is known that improving the quality and efficiency of the educational process is the basis of our future development. For this, every parent, teacher, and coach must first of all see a person in the person of each child. Based on this simple requirement, we should accept that the main goal and task of the education sector should be to raise our children to be perfect people who have the ability to think independently and broadly. This requires the harmonious conduct of educational work."

As we said above, the requirements for education are huge. It is impossible to fulfill these requirements without applying advanced modern technologies to the educational process.

In order to study the level of use of modern technologies in physical education lessons, we asked a group of physical education teachers (total of 20 teachers participated) with the following questions:

1. What do you mean by modern technologies of education?
2. Do you use modern pedagogical technologies of education in your classes?
3. Tell the difference between traditional education and lessons based on pedagogical technologies.
4. How do you understand interactive methods? Give examples.

We evaluated the answers based on the following criteria:

1. It is "very good" if he understands modern technologies well, uses them in his classes, knows how to distinguish them from traditional education and knows interactive methods;
2. It is "good" if he has an understanding of modern technologies, uses them in his experience and knows how they differ from traditional education and knows some interactive methods;
3. Understands modern technology, but sometimes uses it, if not familiar with interactive methods "medium".
4. Does not know and does not use modern technologies, sometimes uses interactive methods "badly".
5. Prefers traditional methods of education and is generally not interested in modern technologies "very bad".

The analysis of responses is shown in the table below:

Table 1. The level of use of modern technologies by physical education teachers in education: (in % of respondents)

No	"very good"	"good"	"medium"	"bad"	"too bad"
	5	10	15	25	45

The analysis of the table shows that in most of the schools we surveyed, the organization of the educational process based on modern technologies is slow.

When it comes to modern technologies, many complain about the lack of computers at school. With this, they want to justify the fact that they do not use modern technologies in education. However, there are 2 different ways of using pedagogical technologies in education.

The first is to achieve a guaranteed result by designing lessons without computer technologies, and the second is to organize lessons with the help of computers.

Therefore, it is possible to organize classes using modern technologies even without computers.

The characteristic aspects of the lesson, its difference from other forms of physical education are as follows.

It is clearly expressed, didactically directed, conditioned by the solution of the educational task.

The leadership role of the teacher, who is focused on teaching the subject and educating students.

Rigorous study and setting of student performance and workload standards.

Continuity of employees and uniformity of their age.

The organization of such a teaching process imposes certain requirements on the modern physical education class.

1. The teacher must provide each lesson with a high-level idea. Therefore, it is necessary to plan a modern lesson with complex tasks. Tasks should be defined and differentiated. It is necessary to conduct them on the basis of knowledge of individual mental and physical characteristics of students' development.

2. Each lesson is closely connected with the previous and subsequent lessons and should form a lesson system. When learning new material, teachers need to review and reinforce the previous material and prepare to learn the next material. Such systems ensure the sequence of solving educational tasks.

3. The modern lesson is distinguished by the fact that students' activities are well organized independently. The teacher successively equips them with academic skills, independent knowledge and self-control, the formation of movement culture, and at the same time educates the need for regular physical exercise.

4. All this is done on the basis of color work discipline. The diversity, sources, methods and methods used by the teacher, the organization of the activities of the students, are modern teaching methods. Lessons should never be organized in the same template.

5. It is a condition of efficiency that all students can easily reach movement activities throughout each lesson.

6. In the physical education lesson, the teacher should organize the lesson using "Brainstorming", "General brainstorming", "Cluster", "6x6x6", "Working with red and green cards" and other interactive methods.

7. It is necessary to ensure that the teacher has a knowledge control system in each lesson, determines the knowledge and skills of students in each part of the lesson, evaluates and develops physical quality at the end of the teaching process.

8. There are many requirements for passing the class: educational material, hygienic, aesthetic, will-psychological, and others.

The mentioned requirements are derived from the general and methodical principles of physical education and are mandatory for classes in all classes.

In conclusion, it can be said that physical education classes cannot be imagined without modern pedagogical technology. Therefore, it is necessary for all teachers to approach this matter seriously, creatively and eloquently.

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